

Turkish soft power in the Erdoğan era: conception, performance and adaptation

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Abstract

Turkish soft power has experienced a decline over the last decade. The existing literature has mostly neglected the assessment of the influence of both the leader's conception and domestic and international changes on Turkish soft power. Addressing this issue, this article aims to answer the following research question: How did Erdoğan's conception and performance of his role influence the evolution of Turkish soft power from 2013 to 2023? 2013 is the year the Gezi protests highlighted Erdoğan's authoritarianism, denigrating his reputation both nationally and internationally, and representing a turning point in Turkish politics. The year 2023 coincides with the centenary of the Turkish Republic, while also marking nearly two decades of Erdoğan's uninterrupted rule. The methodology we use combines the analysis of primary sources - official documents, reports and soft power indices - and secondary sources, based on the assumptions of role theory, namely role conception, role expectations, role adaptation and role performance. Despite Erdoğan's investment in increasing the number of Turkish embassies and consulates, strengthening development aid, awarding scholarships and institutes to promote Turkish culture and language abroad, among other things, this has not translated into an improvement in Turkish soft power. In practice, external expectations of Erdoğan's role reflect the fact that these initiatives have not been able to counter the dissatisfaction felt abroad with the departure from democratic ideals that has accompanied the Turkish leader's consolidation of power.

Keywords

Atatürk; conception and performance; Erdoğan; role theory; soft power; Türkiye

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Introduction

Turkish cultural diplomacy has been the subject of much research, with the focus on Turkish television series. In 2018, Turkish television programs were seen in more than 100 countries, generating revenues of around 350 million dollars a year. Ağırseven and Öрки (2017) concluded that cultural industries - namely Turkish television series - are effective in attracting tourists to the country as well as improving the perception of Türkiye around the world.

Köselerli (2017) investigated the impact of new media on cultural diplomacy. In his research, the author examined the content of the official Twitter accounts of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, concluding that it has an extraordinary capacity to renew its cultural diplomacy. More recently, Pothou (2020) carried out a study to understand why Turkish series are so successful among Greek audiences. The author concluded that while Turkish series were well received in Greece, the same was not true of Turkish citizens. In fact, the latter generated negative perceptions among the Greek public.

Among the studies of Turkish foreign policy, Neo-Ottomanism has been substantially analyzed as one of the main foreign policy doctrines, highlighting the contributions of Hristov (2019), Ciftci and Yavuz (2021) and Wastnidge (2019). Nonetheless, the literature reveals the absence of studies that could lead to a definition of Turkish identity, including how Türkiye sees itself and how it is perceived by others. Drawing on such a gap, this paper attempts to answer the following research question: How did Erdoğan's conception and performance of his role influence the evolution of Turkish soft power from 2013 to 2023? The time frame on which this paper is based covers the period from 2013 to 2023.

As Çevik (2019) admits, there is a growing tendency in the literature to consider that the Gezi Park protests in 2013 were the event that triggered the degradation of Turkish soft power. This event brought to light the authoritarianism of President Recep Erdoğan and revealed the beginning of his crackdown on opponents, becoming a turning point in Turkish politics. The government's reaction to the protests exposed restrictions on freedom of expression, media censorship and repression of the opposition, all of which affected Turkish soft power. The option for 2013 for the beginning of the analysis also took into account the crisis in Syria and the Arab Spring. These events had an impact on Turkish foreign policy, due to the security concerns arising from the instability in the region. In turn, the year 2023 coincides with the centenary of the Turkish Republic, while also marking nearly two decades of Erdoğan's uninterrupted rule.

That said, this paper aims to analyze the evolution of Turkish soft power from 2013 to 2023, trying to understand how the conception and performance of Erdoğan's role influenced it during this period. The analysis draws on a qualitative methodology that is based on primary sources, namely soft power indices such as the Soft Power Index 30, official documents and reports, most of which are available in English. In addition, data from the Turkish Cooperation and Coordination Agency (TIKA), among others, will be used to understand social, humanitarian, educational, economic and cultural aspects. Secondary sources include papers from scientific journals, books and sections of books.

Role theory will be the theoretical-conceptual framework used in this paper. Holsti (1970) pioneered the application of role theory to the field of International Relations (IR) after it had been used in Sociology and related disciplines. Role theory includes several key concepts: role conception, role expectations, role adaptation, and role performance.

Role conception represents the actor's idea of themselves, i.e. the way they see themselves. According to Holsti (1970), role conception consists of the actor's understanding of their own positions and functions, as well as the behavior that best suits them. Role theory includes the conception of the domestic role, which corresponds to the perceptions of political decision-makers about the position of their states in the international system (Wish apud Silva and Labriola, 2019: 86). These are, in theory,

consensual with regard to the role a country should play in the international sphere (Thies, 2015). Holsti (1970) studied conceptions of the domestic role through the speeches of political decision-makers. In this way, discourse analysis is of great importance to role theory. According to Pilch (2012), the speeches of Turkish policymakers mirror conceptions of Türkiye's domestic role, specifically the term Neo-Ottomanism, used to define Türkiye's current foreign policy despite not being an official government ideology (Alekseevich, 2018). Türkiye has been redefining its domestic role as well as its foreign policy to better accommodate the demands of the current international order. With the arrival of the AKP to power, the narrative of Turkish foreign policy has been changing. Conceptions of the domestic role are "multiple and dynamic" (Holsti, 1970: 254): a country can have different conceptions of the domestic role, and these can change depending on domestic or international circumstances.

Pilch (2012) identified several conceptions of the role that allow us to understand Turkish foreign policy and the way the country sees itself, namely: regional leader, regional protector, mediator-integrator, collaborator of regional and global subsystems, model state and faithful ally. According to the author, the changes in Turkish foreign policy that took place after the AKP came to power in 2002 produced new conceptions of the domestic role and a new foreign policy discourse, Neo-Ottomanism. Pilch (2012) concluded that role theory is useful in the study of Türkiye's foreign policy, particularly when looking at the country's domestic role.

A second component of role theory concerns role expectations. These consist of "norms, beliefs and preferences regarding the performance of any individual in a social position in relation to individuals occupying other positions" (Thies, 2008:9). In other words, in the case of this paper, role expectations concern the expectations that other countries have of Türkiye.

Role adaptation, on the other hand, refers to possible changes in role performance (Harnisch et al., 2011). In other words, role adaptation means the way in which the country under study (Türkiye) adapts its vision of itself - its role - to meet the expectations of third parties. An example of this role adaptation is the change in Turkish foreign policy in its relations with the United States of America (USA). Until 2013, Türkiye enjoyed good relations with the US. However, the relationship between the two suffered a setback when the US began supporting the Kurdistan Workers' Party (PKK) in Syria. This led to an adjustment in Turkish foreign policy, which resulted in a rapprochement with Russia.

Finally, role performance corresponds, according to Harnisch et al., to the "political behavior of the actor in the social context" (2011:114). In other words, it is the way in which the country plays its role. In turn, according to Holsti, domestic role performance is the foreign policy behavior of governments. This includes "patterns of attitudes, decisions, responses, roles and commitments towards other states" (Holsti, 1970: 245). It should be noted that both soft power and role theory have as their common denominator the dynamics of image, the perception of both the 'self' and the 'other', as well as interdependence in the interaction between actors. By analyzing the constituent elements of role theory mentioned above, we can see that this conceptual lens offers tools for understanding how Turkish soft power influences the perceptions and expectations of the 'self' and the 'other'.

This paper is divided into two sections. The first will focus on the rise and consolidation of Erdoğan and the AKP in power, while the second assesses the beginning of the decrease of Türkiye's soft power. Finally, the conclusion will answer the research question while stating some major findings.

The Evolution of Soft Power in the Erdoğan era

In order to understand the Turkish context in the Erdoğan era, it is important to analyze the country's domestic and external situation, which led to the rise of the Turkish leader. Domestically, the economic crisis (2000-2001) was a turning point as it accelerated the process of both economic and democratic

reforms with a view to Türkiye's possible accession to the EU (Onis, 2003). In fact, the majority of Turks supported this accession in the hope of an effective way out of the economic crisis in which the country found itself (*Ibid.*). Türkiye's reforms in the 2000s, as a result of its EU application process, boosted Turkish soft power by improving the rule of law, religious freedoms and government transparency (Çevik, 2019). In this way, Türkiye's pro-EU foreign policy orientation strengthened the image that the government's priority should be economic reform and foreign policy, rather than Islamic resurgence (Kirdiş, 2016).

These changes reflect an adaptation of Türkiye's role to international expectations, in this case from the EU. In addition, they attest to the ability of democratic reforms to generate soft power, something that has increased considerably since the AKP came to power in 2002, becoming one of the party's foreign policy priorities (Yenokyan, 2023). At the international level, September 11, 2001, reinforced Türkiye's importance to the West, especially in terms of security.

Since his first term in office in 2002, Erdoğan's party (AKP) has taken new reform decisions on the Kurdish issue, including granting more rights to minorities and gradually disarming the PKK rebels. This initial attempt to include the Kurds can be seen as a strategy by the party to attract more conservative voters of Kurdish origin (Institute for Security and Development Policy, 2016). On the other hand, the expectation of EU membership would allow Türkiye to simultaneously develop a more balanced relationship with the US and play a more measured and constructive role at regional level. In short, domestic and external changes in this period contributed to the transition from a coercive role to one of a potentially benign and constructive regional power (Onis, 2003).

The goal of EU membership was also reflected in the government's policies on cultural diplomacy, which felt the need to improve the perception of EU public opinion towards Türkiye. Thus, Turkish public diplomacy, especially in the cultural sphere, has been strengthened in the EU, visible, among other things, in art exhibitions and film screenings (Muter, 2018). In this context, the Yunus Emre Foundation (YEE) was created in 2007 and was the first official institution in terms of Turkish cultural diplomacy. Its aim is to disseminate Turkish culture, history and language, as well as providing scientific exchange between Türkiye and other states. Although other institutions existed before it with the aim of developing ties with foreign countries, the Yunus Emre Foundation was the first state organization to do so consistently, both domestically and internationally. In practice, this institute is one of the greatest instruments of Turkish cultural diplomacy, nation branding and an element of Türkiye's prestige abroad (Szyszlak, 2021).

During Erdoğan's first and second terms, in addition to the YEE, there was a greater focus on other institutions as soft power tools, such as the Turkish Cooperation and Coordination Agency (TİKA) (Szyszlak, 2021). In 2011, TİKA was restructured in order to improve its effectiveness in cooperation and coordination. The agency has shown particular interest in intervening in areas that once belonged to the former Ottoman empire, which is consistent with the Erdoğan government's foreign policy visions that focus on the Ottoman heritage and its relations with the Balkans, the Middle East and Central Asia (Akıllı and Çelenk, 2019). The number of TİKA projects almost quadrupled in 2011 compared to 2002, which is testament to the AKP's efforts to promote a positive image of Türkiye. Furthermore, the budget allocated to this agency's initiatives has also increased exponentially since 2002, when the AKP came to power. In fact, during the period from 2003 to 2013 the investment made was five times higher compared to the period from 1992 to 2002 (Akıllı and Çelenk, 2019). Thus, investments of around 85 million dollars in 2002 increased to over a billion dollars in 2011 (Turkish Development Assistance Report 2018, 2019).

Although Türkiye has experienced difficulties - particularly with the economic crises of the 1990s and between 2000 and 2001 - the growth of the economy, stability and the process of democratization from this decade onwards allowed the country to attract the attention of various players (Ayhan, 2018). In fact, the crisis of 2000-2001 led to reforms in political and economic institutions, which led to recovery between 2002 and 2007. This was encouraged by two essential pillars: the successful implementation of reforms supported by the International Monetary Fund (IMF) and the opening of negotiations for EU membership. However, this successful period of economic reforms, prudent economic policies, public debt reduction and gross domestic product growth saw fewer positive developments from the 2007 elections onwards (Macovei, 2009).

The AKP tried to build a credible image of Türkiye, convincing other players that the country was still a democracy. On the other hand, foreign policy, more oriented towards the economic sphere than security, played an active role in important economic and political fora and multilateral and regional cooperation agreements, which allowed Türkiye's image to be strengthened as a middle power. This proactive Turkish soft power confirms Erdoğan's conception of Türkiye's role in extending its area of influence, both regionally and internationally. In this way, Türkiye would cumulatively assume various roles: "regional leader", "protector" and "mediator" (Gürzel, 2014).

When he came to power, Erdoğan's party was made up of members with different ideologies but who converged in their discontent with the secular parties and their austerity policies. However, there was a suspicion that these were just promises, taking advantage of the bad political and economic situation the country was going through as a result of the 2001 economic crisis (Yeşilada, 2023). The AKP's image as a reformist and pro-EU party allowed it to win over voters, both among the more conservative and those who did not identify as religious but were more liberal. This happened because both saw themselves represented by the party: for the liberals, democratic reforms in an attempt to join the EU, and for the conservatives, the safeguarding of their religious rights (Kirdiş, 2016). Thus, the party managed to adapt its role to the expectations of the domestic public.

During AKP's first term (2002 to 2007), efforts were made towards Türkiye's possible accession to the EU, which culminated in Ankara opening negotiations with Brussels in 2005. These actions managed to convince the more skeptical electorate that the party presented itself as moderate in religious terms (Kirdiş, 2016). The country has produced Middle East policies that respect the region's status quo by not intervening militarily in regional conflicts. Instead, Türkiye has opted to use its soft power to try to resolve possible conflicts in the region, such as between Syria and Israel. In this way, Turkish foreign policymakers managed, especially in the AKP's first term, to combine Türkiye's interests in the Middle East with the orientation of its policies towards the West (Özpek and Demirağ, 2014).

Although Erdoğan often argued religion should not be mixed with politics, in practice the situation was different, as he worked hard to gradually remove his opponents from within the party, as well as to undo previous reforms using constitutional amendments, favoritism and corruption to consolidate his power. When the AKP was created, great care was taken to disguise references to religion, often under the pretext of defending political and civil rights. In addition, the AKP was also pro-EU and less nationalist and Islamic than previous parties. After its second election in 2007, most reforms designed to achieve the goal of EU membership were undone, leading to the gradual creation of an authoritarian regime centered on the person of Erdoğan (Yeşilada, 2023). Thus, the turnaround in reforms slowed down the accession process, which was felt in Turkish foreign policy (Kirdiş, 2016).

As a result, during its second term in office (2007-2011), the party went through a unique period in which, on the domestic front, it saw its electorate grow, thus governing without coalitions. However, at the same time, the AKP was being shut down by the Turkish Constitutional Court, and on

the external front there was a noticeable slowdown in negotiations for Türkiye's accession to the EU (Kirdiş, 2016).

In the 2007 elections, the Kurdish question and political Islam were central themes. The year before the elections, 2006, public television - Turkish Radio and Television (TRT) - had inaugurated a Kurdish-language channel - TRT Kurdî. Despite the improved quality of both TRT World and TRT Kurdî, these channels were unable to compete with others of their kind, such as Al Jazeera. This has made it difficult to spread Türkiye's narrative/model to other societies (Guida and Göksel, 2018). Despite this, the creation of the Kurdish channel attests to an effort on the part of the AKP to welcome and disseminate Kurdish identity abroad. In fact, during the AKP's second term, in 2007, Erdoğan announced resolutions to meet some Kurdish demands, namely to bring PKK members back to Türkiye from both Iraq and various bases in Europe. Although such attempts to adapt the role to the expectations of the Kurds seemed to represent a turning point in the Kurdish question, it only produced a perception of victory on the part of the Kurds, which led to the arrest of some PKK members and the return of others to Iraq.

In his efforts to appease the Kurdish question, Erdoğan also abolished the need for visas for Syrians traveling to Türkiye, and vice versa. However, with the Arab Spring in Syria, a new danger arose, as the measure made it easier for Syrians to enter Türkiye. This was to have an impact on the dynamics of relations between Türkiye and Syria. Later, in 2010, the reform proposals that the AKP presented to the Turkish parliament did not mention the Kurds (Bengio, 2011), attesting to the decline of policies involving this minority, not without an impact on Turkish soft power. In fact, the Kurdish problem has also affected relations between the EU and Türkiye, especially with regard to human rights in the country, which was one of the biggest obstacles to Türkiye's accession to the EU. For its part, the EU was concerned that the PKK had formed networks in some EU countries. In 2002, the PKK was considered a terrorist organization by the EU in the wake of September 11, 2001. This situation therefore compromised perceptions of Türkiye in some EU countries, and vice versa. Thus, the Kurdish issue, which had previously been seen by Türkiye as a domestic security issue, became one of the country's main concerns, both domestically and internationally (Bengio, 2011).

As far as political Islam is concerned, 2007 was also marked by accusations from the Turkish army general staff that Erdoğan was pursuing a camouflaged Islamic agenda (Polat, 2009). At the start of the AKP's second term in office, Turkish identity was redefined in the country's foreign policy - adapting its role - by distancing itself from Türkiye's passive stance and re-establishing dynamic and broad relations with its neighbors (Kirdiş, 2016). Following on from this, Davutoğlu introduced the concept of "strategic depth" (in 2001), which focuses on Türkiye's geographical position. It emphasizes Turkish history, namely its Ottoman past and cultural relations with the Balkans, the Middle East and Central Asia (Rabasa & Larrabee, 2008 apud Yenokyan, 2023). In addition to this doctrine, Turkish soft power at the time also included the "zero problems with neighbors" policy, which sought to resolve frictions with nearby countries by improving relations with them (Yenokyan, 2023).

This reorientation of Turkish foreign policy also represented an adaptation of the role to the expectations of the domestic public. In fact, the Turks felt that Türkiye was passively accommodating the demands of the powers that be - particularly the Western powers - even if these diverged from Turkish interests. Thus, by reorienting foreign policy, the AKP was able to win support from different political orientations driven by nationalist sentiments (Kirdiş, 2016).

Despite the "zero problems with neighbors" policy, the dispute with Cyprus was and still is a major obstacle to Türkiye's accession to the EU (Euronews, 2023). In 1960, Cyprus gained its independence from the UK under a constitution based on power-sharing between Greek and Turkish

Cypriots, with the UK being able to intervene on the island together with Türkiye and Greece. Cyprus has been divided since 1974, when Türkiye invaded the north of the island in response to a military coup backed by the Greek government. The island was thus divided: one third in the north under Turkish-Cypriot rule and two thirds in the south governed by an internationally recognized Greek-Cypriot government (BBC, 2023).

An important event in the history of this conflict took place in 2003 when Turkish and Greek Cypriots crossed the line dividing the island - the Green Line - as a result of the Turkish Cypriot authorities easing border restrictions. In turn, in 2004 Cyprus became a member of the EU but as a divided island (BBC, 2023). When it came to power in 2002, the AKP advocated a confederal solution to the Cyprus issue, i.e. reunification of the island, which represented a major shift in Turkish foreign policy accompanied by a positive perception of Türkiye in the EU (Özertem, 2021). This stance is in line with the more moderate behavior that the AKP adopted when it came to power, since support for a confederation in the case of Cyprus presupposes an effort at conciliation. On the other hand, the defense of a confederal solution presupposes the preservation of state autonomy.

However, after several years of negotiations, Türkiye decided to return to its initial stance towards Cyprus. Özertem (2021) believes that this change in Türkiye's position is the result of a multitude of factors, including the decades-long negotiations, which have diminished the EU's transformative capacity in Türkiye, and the changing balance of power in the region in which the country is located. In addition to these, there are the low prospects of Türkiye joining the EU and the discovery of hydrocarbons near the island. The Cyprus issue continues to be a sore point in Türkiye-EU relations. This problem intensified after Cyprus joined the EU, as the Cyprus issue became part of the EU's internal agenda. In addition, with EU membership, the Greek Cypriots gained influence over EU decisions due to their veto power, which further complicated Türkiye-EU relations. At this juncture, pro-EU policies gradually began to move away from the AKP's priorities (Özertem, 2021).

On the other hand, from 2011 onwards, the Arab uprisings gave rise to even greater security concerns in the foreign policy of the states, since these dynamics led to an escalation of tensions between Türkiye and other states, namely Israel, Greece, Cyprus and Egypt. In turn, Türkiye began to use its hard power in the region in search of greater security, especially in the second half of the 2010s (Özertem, 2021).

In light of the above, it is considered that the "golden age" of Turkish public diplomacy took place between 2007 and 2013. In the following years, its diplomatic capacity declined radically as a result of internal political instability and Türkiye's successive international isolation. As a result, Turkish soft power experienced a period of decline, as we will analyze below.

Türkiye's new era - the turning point

From 2010 to 2016, Turkish soft power suffered a significant decline due to domestic and international events. In the domestic sphere, there was the centralization of power, the decline of democratic values and the resurgence of the Kurdish conflict. In the international sphere, Türkiye found it difficult to achieve its goals, while the Islamization of politics continued (Szyszlak, 2021).

To better analyze the evolution of Turkish soft power, we turned to The Soft Power 30, as well as the one developed by the Institute for Government (IFG) in collaboration to the Monocle magazine, which gives us a more homogeneous view of the perceptions of the external public towards Türkiye. Thus, the IFG-Monocle 2010 index placed Türkiye in 25th place in 2010 in terms of soft power. The report highlighted the change in Türkiye's dependence on hard power to a more soft power-oriented approach in the international sphere. Domestically, the reforms resulting from the country's EU

candidacy were highlighted. At the international level, the report points out that the evolution of Turkish foreign policy has sought to serve three objectives: to strengthen relations with neighboring countries, to maximize its privileged geographical position between East and West, and to instrumentalize Ottoman nostalgia in the conduct of foreign policy. At the time, Türkiye's main foreign policy objective was to assert itself as a regional or even global leader through soft power (Ibid).

An impactful event in Turkish soft power was the awarding of the 2010 Chatham House Prize to then-President Abdullah Gül for his role in pushing for Türkiye's EU accession reforms. In addition to these, the former president was also honored for his dedication to bringing stability and prosperity to the region of which Türkiye is geographically a part (Turkish Forum, 2010).

At the end of 2010, the Arab countries were the scene of unique and radical political transformations, known as the Arab Springs. By virtue of its geographical position and growing relevance in the region, Türkiye was equally influential in these events, as it was greatly influenced by them. In this way, the Arab Springs constituted an obstacle for Turkish foreign policy, since it was based on the principles of "zero problems" with neighbors, justice, freedom and non-interference in the country's domestic affairs. For this reason, poor management of this issue could lead to Türkiye's loss of credibility (Khalifa, 2017).

In 2011, according to the IfG-Monocle index, Türkiye moved up from 25th place to 23rd, maintaining the stance described the previous year. The changes to consolidate its democracy, the foreign policy based on the three pillars listed above and the ambitions to assert itself as a regional and global power through the use of soft power are once again noteworthy. The 2011 report also mentions the Turkish Public Diplomacy Agency, following the growth of Türkiye's diplomatic network. Created in 2008, this agency is a mechanism that aims to improve the foundations of Turkish soft power, namely public institutions and foreign policy (IfG-Monocle index, n.d.).

In fact, foreign aid, as well as humanitarian and development aid, is by nature an essential component of Turkish soft power (Çevik, 2019). It represents an effort to minimize the negative effects of declining political values by compensating for them with the development of cultural and humanitarian tools. As we analyzed earlier, from more than one billion dollars in investments in TİKA in 2011, government support for this agency has increased over the years, reaching more than eight billion dollars in 2020 (Turkish Development Assistance Report 2018-2021). In turn, there has also been an increase in the number of TİKA offices (from 25 offices in 2011 to 62 in 2020) and in the number of countries to which Turkish foreign aid has reached (in 2011 Turkish aid was extended to more than 100 countries, increasing to around 170 in 2020). The projects and activities carried out by this agency allow Türkiye to be perceived in a more positive light, in turn contributing to an increase in Turkish soft power (Akıllı and Çelenk, 2019). Thus, we can infer that TİKA has been strengthened, taking on a more dynamic role since 2002. Despite the difficulties, both internationally and domestically, Türkiye has continued to make efforts to contribute aid to other states, being one of the most generous countries in the world (Akıllı and Çelenk, 2019).

When the Arab Springs broke out in the Middle East in 2011, Turkish leaders' perceptions of these events were mostly positive, as Türkiye supported all grassroots-based changes in the region. However, the Arab Spring in Syria began to have implications for Türkiye, through the rise of the Islamic State in Syria and Iraq, and the re-emergence of the PKK, highlighting long-standing problems in Turkish foreign policy in the Middle East, namely the Kurdish question and Türkiye's Sunni orientation. These obstacles have therefore led to the loss of Türkiye's mediating role in the region (Işıksal, 2018). Thus, the developments of the Arab Spring led to the end of the "zero problems with neighbors" policy (Muter, 2018), which was an adaptation of Türkiye's role to the situation in the region.

During the AKP's third term (2011-2015), the role of identity became increasingly prominent (Kirdiş, 2016). Specifically, Erdoğan emphasized Turkish values, traditions, history and geography as a model for Muslim countries in foreign policy (Yanık, 2012). However, this construction of identity has accentuated the latent polarizations in Turkish society (Kirdiş, 2016). In this mandate, and especially after the Gezi protests in 2013, there was a growing weakness in Turkish soft power. In fact, the increase in ideological polarization in the country has negatively affected both Türkiye's stability and image since 2013.

In turn, the fourth term (2015-2018) was very turbulent, with the coup attempt on October 15, 2016 standing out, which led to a change in the conception of Erdoğan's role and, consequently, in the performance of his foreign policy, which became more nationalistic with the aim of protecting himself from external threats. This stance resulted, among other things, in greater skepticism towards the West and the creation of a narrative that the West was Türkiye's external enemy (Kirdiş, 2016).

According to The Portland Soft Power Index 30, Türkiye was in 28th place in 2015, and in 2016 it failed to make the top 30 soft power countries, ranking 32nd due to domestic and international instability. In practice, Türkiye was gradually becoming an authoritarian regime, repressing critics and driving away opponents, a situation that attracted international attention (Institute for Security and Development Policy, 2016).

Furthermore, on July 15, 2016, the coup attempt to overthrow Erdoğan's government failed, although its repercussions were still latent. Erdoğan and his government blamed the coup on Fethullah Gülen, a former ally of the president, who has been in exile since 1999 for planning a coup attempt (Al Jazeera, 2022). The coup attempt triggered profound political, economic and social changes at the domestic level in Türkiye and, consequently, at the international level. In other words, it impacted both the conception of the role and the performance of the role of Erdoğan's Türkiye.

The main consequence of the coup attempt was the constitutional reform. Approved by referendum with 51 percent of the vote, it was aimed at strengthening Erdoğan's powers, allowing him to bypass parliament and limit rights and freedoms, as well as dismissing thousands of judges and civil servants (Euronews, 2017; Al Jazeera, 2016). These restrictions on freedoms also included the media, with the authorities shutting down more than a hundred media outlets, justifying them with alleged terrorist links, detaining more than 100 journalists and blocking access to Wikipedia. The wave of dismissals did not stop at the media but also encompassed the armed forces with the closure of military academies and the dismissal of thousands of army officers. There were also closures of non-governmental organizations, schools, universities and trade unions (Euronews, 2017).

As a result, Erdoğan's performance of the role has had the main consequence of increasing tensions with the West, particularly with the US and the EU regarding, fundamentally, human rights and the rule of law (Al Jazeera, 2016; Tol et al., 2016). In addition, both the constitutional change, which granted Erdoğan more powers, and the arrests, were perceived by democratic states as a path towards authoritarianism, affecting Türkiye's image in these countries (Tol et al., 2016). As a result of the deterioration of ties with the West, Ankara has sought to deepen relations with non-Western powers, such as Russia and China, as evidenced by the signing of the contract for the purchase of the missile defense system from Russia in 2017, which has shaken relations with NATO.

During the two decades that the AKP has been in power, what many authors, including Yilmaz and Bashirov (2018) and Akyol (2016), have called Erdoğanism has emerged. For Akyol (2016), Erdoğanism refers to the ideology of Erdoğan's government, which aims to replace Kemalism. In fact, Erdoğanism refers to a political regime based on four main pillars: electoral authoritarianism as a

political model; neopatrimonialism as an economic model; populism as a political strategy and Islamism as a political ideology (Yilmaz and Bashirov, 2018).

The successive growth of authoritarianism after the Gezi protests generated harsh condemnation from the West, as well as the consequent weakening of Turkish soft power (Kirişçi apud Muter, 2018). Against this backdrop, let's highlight the European Parliament's demand to halt negotiations on Türkiye's accession to the European Union due to the country's repressive actions, which the European body considered to be exaggerated (Euronews, 2017).

The 2016 Soft Power Index 30 report highlights Türkiye's reputation as a "bridge between the West and the East". According to the report, while on the one hand the country is a tourist attraction, it is also at the forefront of the migration crisis, as well as having difficulty managing the Kurdish issue. Freedom of the press is presented as another weakness of Turkish soft power (The Soft Power Index 30, 2016). In fact, the broadcasting of street protests and clashes by the international media has weakened Türkiye's image, which has begun to be seen as an unstable country with no ability to align itself with the EU's democratic values (Guida and Göksel, 2018). As a charismatic leader, Erdoğan continuously uses digital communication platforms to raise awareness and attract the public. In addition to his platforms, Erdoğan and his party also rely on the support of some media, namely television and newspapers, to convey their narrative (Özışık, 2021).

Despite the obstacles, the 2016 index revealed that Türkiye was the country with the best soft power rating in its region, establishing itself as a regional soft power. Despite successive terrorist attacks that have raised security concerns, the situation has not been a complete deterrent for tourists. In fact, the attraction of Turkish culture is encouraged by the popularity of Turkish television series, which are the driving force behind the development of tourism in the country. Initially, there were no initiatives by the Turkish government to promote the Turkish series. However, given their success and attractiveness, this support came naturally and Turkish television content came to be included in the sphere of cultural diplomacy. In this way, state television channels pay particular attention to the production of historical series, through which international audiences develop an affection for the Ottoman heritage (Yenokyan, 2023).

Dizi - Turkish television dramas - which were broadcast after their success in the Middle East, Balkans, Caucasus, Latin America, Western Europe and North Africa, attest to the improvement in Turkish public diplomacy. This success contributed to Türkiye becoming the world's second largest producer of TV drama content in 2014. The country has shown that it is possible to harmoniously combine traditional Islamic values with modern lifestyles and problems, generating influence by alluding to the Ottoman imperial past (Donelli, 2019).

In 2017, Türkiye was once again one of the 30 countries with the strongest soft power, ranking 30th according to the Soft Power Index 30. The 2017 report highlighted the country's development aid, refugee resettlement and participation in permanent missions within multilateral organizations as strengths of Turkish soft power. In addition, the insightful use of soft power tools is again praised and, as in 2016, Turkish Airlines is highlighted for its role in promoting Türkiye abroad (The Soft Power Index 30, 2017).

Donelli (2019) considers Turkish Airlines to be the most prominent Turkish brand, a symbol of service excellence and modernity. The notoriety of Türkiye and Turkish Airlines itself has grown with sponsorships of both major clubs - notably Manchester United and Barcelona FC - and international competitions in various sports. This has helped spread a positive image of Türkiye abroad (Donelli, 2019). In addition, Turkish Airlines also proves to be an important element of Turkish soft power through its involvement in humanitarian missions, such as transporting aid to Somalia, reinforcing

Türkiye's image as a caring country (Anaz, 2017). Finally, this airline is also relevant in facilitating trade and business, playing an important role in Türkiye's economic diplomacy and strengthening relations with other countries (Selçuk, 2012).

On the other hand, the Soft Power Index 30 of 2017 highlights, as a weakness, the negative international perceptions of Türkiye following the referendum that gave Erdoğan more powers, and the limitations on the press resulting from the coup attempt (The Soft Power 30, 2017). In 2018, Türkiye was once again left out of the 30 countries with the greatest soft power capacity in the world, although it re-entered the ranking the following year. Thus, in 2019 the country rose to 29th place, at a time when it was looking to improve economically after the difficulties of 2018. Türkiye was in the spotlight thanks to the remarkable digital interaction (on social media) of Erdoğan's followers abroad. In addition, the dynamic stance of both Turkish embassies and ministries on social media and the continued growth of the Turkish diplomatic network contributed to improving the country's score in this ranking. In addition, despite international criticism of Turkish policies and a domestic situation marked by the concentration of power and consequent reduction in individual freedoms, the report reveals that this has not reduced the number of foreign tourists in the country. However, the AKP's loss of Türkiye's most important chambers reveals the domestic public's discontent with the government. Finally, the report points to weaknesses in foreign perceptions of Turkish foreign policy and Erdoğan's narrative (The Soft Power 30, 2019).

In short, the coup attempt was a turning point for Turkish soft power, signaling a democratic retreat, tensions in relations between Türkiye and the West and the strengthening of pro-Islamic and nationalist sentiments (Szyslak, 2021). In turn, an analysis of the evolution of Turkish society in the Erdoğan era shows an attempt to redefine Turkish identity, which involves a search for less secular values alongside the instrumentalization of religion in the service of politics. In this respect, Yeşilada (2023) explains that more traditional societies attach greater importance to religion, unlike more secular ones. Indeed, Türkiye's Islamic heritage has been influenced by both Ottoman heritage and Islam. In the case of the Ottoman heritage, it harks back to a glorious Ottoman past, giving Turks hope that they can once again be influential in the world. In this sense, the conception of Erdoğan's role and Turkish expectations of him are influenced by his imperial past, as well as by the country's culture and history. As these elements are deeply rooted in society's perceptions, they are unlikely to change (Ozkan, 2021).

Conclusion

Based on the analytical contributions provided by role theory, this paper sought to answer the following research question: How did Erdoğan's conception and performance of the role influence the evolution of Turkish soft power from 2013 to 2023? In this sense, we have reached some important conclusions.

The first major conclusion of this paper is that 2013 was a turning point, especially after the Gezi protests, which negatively affected both the stability and image of the country. Erdoğan's Türkiye, and inherently Turkish soft power, have been subject to a redefinition of identity due to the greater weight given by the leader to Turkish values, traditions, history and geography in foreign policy. In practice, the new foreign policy doctrine "New Türkiye", idealized by the AKP, expresses an idea of change and rupture compared to "Old Türkiye". Like 2013, 2016 would also be a significant milestone in the evolution of Turkish soft power. In fact, the attempted coup d'état in 2016 represented a turning point in domestic and international politics. It marked a democratic setback, tensions in relations between Türkiye and the West, and the growth of a pro-Islamic and nationalist stance. The change in

the conception of the role and performance of foreign policy is, in essence, the continuation of the identity redefinition that was already taking place under Erdoğan. This redefinition - which involves the search for less secular values and the instrumentalization of religion in the service of politics - was considerably intensified in response to the coup attempt in 2016, with notable impacts on Turkish soft power.

As a second conclusion, although the events mentioned above have contributed to a weakening of Turkish soft power, it would be unfair not to recognize Erdoğan's various efforts in the field of culture and development aid. In this sense, both Turkish cultural and humanitarian diplomacy have been seen as tools to mitigate external perceptions of the country. Our analysis of soft power indices has allowed us to specifically highlight the contribution of Turkish series, Turkish Airlines, development aid, refugee resettlement and participation in humanitarian missions in an attempt to improve Türkiye's image in the world. The Turkish series, which have considerably boosted tourism in Türkiye, have created the image of a country that is able to harmoniously combine traditional Islamic values with a modern lifestyle, through its references to the Ottoman imperial past. This explains why, even in the face of terrorist attacks in the country and international criticism of the concentration of power, tourists have not stopped visiting Türkiye. In fact, the attraction of Turkish culture is encouraged by the popularity of Turkish television series. Even so, the commitment to developing cultural tools is insufficient to compensate for the decline in the country's reputation caused by political conduct that is not well received by the international community.

Finally, as a result of the above, our final conclusion is that Erdoğan's soft power in Türkiye has been more effective domestically than abroad. In fact, in recent years, Turkish soft power has become increasingly populist, characterized by the exploitation of Islamism to the detriment of traditional secularism. This conception of the role is produced at the cost of frustrating the expectations of a West that sold the illusion of a European identity to the country, but which did not come to fruition. As a result, not having been matched by the EU, but also by the US, Erdoğan's Türkiye has chosen to deepen its Asian identity - in which China and Russia matter as alternative poles to Western values - at the same time as the instrumentalization of Islam has contributed to the consolidation of the Turkish leader in power.

As a contribution to future research, we think it would be useful to look more closely at Turkish cultural diplomacy - in terms of promoting the language, arts and series, and their impact on Turkish soft power - with a focus on Western Europe, a region where these have seen unparalleled growth. A study of Turkish digital diplomacy is also pertinent, specifically the role of digital platforms and social networks, in addition to traditional media, in the development of Türkiye's soft power. As we have seen throughout this paper, the media plays a fundamental role in shaping perceptions, profoundly influencing Turkish soft power.

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